

A Study of Different Recovery Positions of Heart Rate Recovery and Its Comparison between Physically Active and Sedentary Males after Submaximal Exercise

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Abstract:

Aim: This study aimed to find out best postures of recovery and compare it in physically active and sedentary males after submaximal exercise.

Materials and methods: The study was conducted in 40 male subjects with 20 sedentary and 20 physically active individuals. The selected participants were asked to do submaximal cycle exercise test. The heart rate was recorded with the help of electronic blood pressure instrument, first reading was taken after 60 sec and then after 3 mins, 5mins, 7mins and 9 mins of a recovery period. Heart rate recovery was recorded and compared between sedentary and active individuals in three different recovery positions; sitting, supine and active after submaximal exercise.

Result: Supine recovery position was found to be the fastest heart rate recovery position and upright seated recovery position was the slowest heart rate recovery position among sedentary and among physically active individuals after submaximal exercise. When heart rate recovery was compared between sedentary and physically active individuals it was found that physically active individuals recovered heart rate faster than the sedentary individuals in all three heart rate recovery positions. Individuals with regular physical activity showed more effective autonomic activity than the sedentary ones.

Conclusion: This study concluded that better cardiovascular fitness will have faster heart rate recovery after exercise.

Keywords: Heart Rate Recovery, Cardiovascular Fitness, Submaximal Exercise.

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Introduction

The past two decades have seen a much-publicized fitness boom in India. From sales of aerobic dance videotapes to popular participation in marathon running, indicators abound that Indians are interested in “working out.” However, there is also evidence that a very significant proportion of the population, especially the young, engage in little and regular physical activity.

As the hours spent in watching television are increasing, the epidemic rates of obesity and the abundance of energy-saving modern conveniences all testify to the fact that many people live in a sedentary manner. Sedentary lifestyle and physical inactivity represent the high prevalence and public health concern in developed and developing countries [1]. As per center for diseases control and prevention, sedentary lifestyle was defined as no leisure-time physical activity or activities done for

less than 20 minutes or fewer than three times per week. Healthy living and physical fitness are closely related. Keeping active in sports, exercise or everyday chores helps us live longer. Active people also have a more positive outlook towards life and the energy to get things done and make things happen. Lifelong rewarding in just an investment of thirty minutes a day [2].

Physical activity is known to improve physical fitness and to reduce morbidity and mortality from numerous chronic ailments [3]. To enjoy a long and healthy life, everyone should make lifestyle choices that include a healthy diet, regular exercise and maintaining a normal weight. Getting enough rest after exercise is very important for high-level performance. The body repairs and strengthens itself in the time between workouts, and continuous training can weaken the strongest athletes.

Recovery has different effects some are physiological and some are psychological. Physical rest is necessary so that the muscles can repair, rebuild, and strengthen. Recovery time after any high-intensity training program is important because this is the time that the body adapts to the stress of exercise and the real training effect takes place. Recovery also allows the body to repair the damaged tissue and replenish energy stores. Exercise or any other physical activity that causes changes in the body such as muscle tissue breakdown and the depletion of energy stores (muscle glycogen) as well as fluid loss and various effects on respiratory rate and heart rate. Recovery time allows these stores to be replenished and allows tissue repair to occur and recovery of respiratory rate and heart rate.

When we engage in physical activity, the heart needs to meet the demands of the working muscles, which need oxygenated blood for any prolonged activity. The time it takes for our heart to recover from any given physical exertion is known as your heart rate recovery time. Heart rate recovery is important because it is one of the signs of overall cardiovascular fitness [4].

Effect of posture on heart rate recovery has not been clearly studied so far in Indian setup. The effects of different body postures on heart rate recovery after high-intensity exercise have partly been described by Takahashi who showed accelerated HRR in the supine compared with the upright sitting position. A more recent in-depth analysis by Buchheit and colleagues examined the effects of four body postures (standing, sitting, supine and supine with elevated legs) on post-exercise parasympathetic reactivation [5]. They showed poor HRR values in the standing upright position and no improvement in the supine position with elevated legs as opposed to plain supine position [5].

The effects of the upright sitting position with active recovery on heart rate recovery after exercise have not yet been examined. Previous research has suggested faster HRR after exercise in well-trained athletes or physically active and fit individuals [6,7]. So here we are trying to relate HRR in sitting active recovery, supine position and sitting positions of recovery and find out which recovery posture is best for the heart rate recovery after submaximal exercise and comparing it in physically active and sedentary males.

Aims and Objectives

Aim: To find out best postures of recovery and compare it in physically active and sedentary males after submaximal exercise.

Objectives:

- To find out and compare relation between

heart rate recovery and position of recovery in physically active and sedentary males.

- To find out and compare recovery of heart rate in the supine position in physically active and sedentary males.
- To find out and compare recovery of heart rate in sitting position in physically active and sedentary males.
- To find out and compare recovery of heart rate in sitting active position in physically active and sedentary males.

Materials and Methods

The study protocol was approved by Institutional Ethics Committee and was in accordance with the Helsinki Declaration for studies on humans.

The study was carried out in 20 physically active and 20 sedentary males and a total of 40 healthy adult male volunteers in the age group of 18-35 years with normal BMI who visited the fitness center having treadmill facility and had not yet started to exercise but was keen to exercise and ready to volunteer for the study. Volunteers were selected on basis of inclusion criteria.

The same volunteers were chosen as both study as well as a control group in order to minimize the confounding factors and make the study reproducible. Informed written consent was obtained from all the volunteers prior to testing. Volunteers were explained in detail about the test procedure and a diagram was shown for the better understanding of the tests. Outcome measures were resting heart rate and submaximal exercise heart rate recovery measured in three different positions; sitting, active recovery and supine position.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Healthy individuals with age group 18-35 years.
2. Physically fit participants assessed by standard PAR-Q Questionnaires.
3. Normal BMI adults of 18.5 to 24.9 kg/m² according to WHO classification.
4. Physically active: Participants with physical activity who are involved in various organized high and vigorous intensity activities percenters for disease control and prevention and American College of Sports Medicine guidelines (e.g. football, basketball, handball, gym) for past one year [8].
5. Sedentary: Participants with low-level physical activity who were not engaged in any organized physical activity for the last six months before the start of the investigation [8].

Exclusion criteria:

1. History of chronic heart disease, diabetes mellitus of any duration.
2. Acute illnesses like respiratory tract infection,

- gastroenteritis.
3. Influences of any medication.
 4. Diseases like asthma, bronchitis.
 5. Recent & past history of osteopenia, fracture, arthritis, sprain.

Procedure:

The whole procedure of the study was explained and a written consent of the participants was obtained and involvement of participants was on a volunteer basis.

At an ambient temperature in a quiet room every participant were examined and their anthropometric data were obtained and were also checked for any acute or chronic illness and history was taken and participants self-validated that they don't have any acute or chronic co-morbidity and participants were asked to fill par-q questionnaire for finding out their physical fitness for undergoing experiment protocol.

On the day of study participants were informed about the general procedures which included informing the person about the type and purpose of the test and they were instructed to avoid any strenuous activity for 24 hours prior to testing and to avoid a heavy meal, caffeine, or nicotine within 2 to 3 hours of testing.

Then participants were asked to do submaximal cycle exercise test [8]. i.e. limited period of symptomless exercise up to HR of ~86% of age-predicted maximum HR which is defined as 220 minus age of participant (Age-predicted maximal heart rate) (HRmax) [9] on cycle ergometer and then every participant was asked to undergo a recovery protocol i.e. Upright seated position; the participant's feet were placed on a platform in front of the pedals while both legs were flexed at the knee at about 90°. The arms were placed over the thighs [5,8]. Participants were asked to move in suggested recovery protocol under 5sec. The heart

rate was recorded with the help of electronic blood pressure instrument, first reading was taken after 60 sec and then after 3 mins, 5mins, 7mins and 9 mins of a recovery period. Then some rest was given for the full recovery of the participant and then again participant was asked to perform a similar exercise.

Seated position with active recovery; after exercise cessation participants, were asked to continue to ride the cycle ergometer but without any workload. Pedalling rate was set at 20 turns per minute [5,8]. Recording of heart rate and other procedures were repeated in the same way as done in upright seated position.

Supine body position, participants were asked to lie facing upwards, flat on the bed which will be located next to the cycle ergometer [5,8].

Recording of heart rate and other procedures were repeated in the same way as done in upright seated position. The "End of test" was considered when recovery of heart rates after submaximal exercise was recorded in all three recovery positions for the individual.

Statistical Analysis

Data were entered in Microsoft Office Excel 2018 and analyzed using the Graph Pad InStat version 4.0. Data were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. Unpaired 't' test was applied for intergroup analysis and paired 't' test for intragroup analysis. A p value of <0.05 was considered significant.

Results

In this study, 40 healthy adults in the age group of 18-35 years of BMI ranging from 18.5 to 24.9 were taken and divided into 2 groups as sedentary and active and their heart rates were measured after submaximal exercise and recovery of heart rates were seen in different recovery positions.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of participants

	Sedentary	Active
Age	24.1	22.25
Weight	62.16	63.78
Height	173.12	173.02
Blood Pressure		
Systolic	117.45	114.2
Diastolic	78.5	71.5
BMI	20.7	21.29
RHR	87.5	72.8

Results after intragroup comparison:

Table 2: Comparison of heart rate recovery in sitting vs supine posture in sedentary individuals after submaximal exercise

	Sitting (Mean \pm SD)	Supine (Mean \pm SD)	P Value
Sedentary	98.9 \pm 7.57	90.05 \pm 5.031	p=0.0002

By paired t-Test, Mean heart rate after submaximal exercise in sitting recovery position after 5 mins were 98.9/min which is statistically significant as compared 90.05/min in supine recovery position in sedentary individuals. P value is 0.0002.

Table 3: Comparison of heart rate recovery in supine vs active posture in sedentary individuals after submaximal exercise.

	Supine (Mean ± SD)	Active (Mean ± SD)	P Value
Sedentary	90.05±5.031	104.65±6.05	p<0.0001

By paired t-test, mean heart rate after submaximal exercise in supine recovery position after 5 mins were 90.05/min which is statistically significant as compared 104.65/min in active recovery position in sedentary individuals. P value is <0.0001.

Table 4: Comparison of heart rate recovery in sitting vs active posture in sedentary individuals after submaximal exercise

	Sitting (Mean ± SD)	Active (Mean ± SD)	P Value
sedentary	98.9±7.57	104.65±6.05	p=0.0056

By paired t-Test, Mean heart rate after submaximal exercise in sitting recovery position after 5 mins were 98.9/min which is statistically significant as compared 104.65/min in active recovery position in sedentary individuals. P value is 0.0056

Table 5: Comparison of heart rate recovery in sitting vs supine posture in active individuals after submaximal exercise

	Sitting (Mean ± SD)	Supine (Mean ± SD)	P Value
Active	91.15±15.11	82.7±9.55	p=0.0111

By paired t-Test, Mean heart rate after submaximal exercise in sitting recovery position after 5 mins were 91.15/min which is statistically significant as compared 82.7/min in supine recovery position in active individuals. P value is 0.0111.

Table 6: Comparison of heart rate recovery in supine vs active posture in active individuals after submaximal exercise

	Supine (Mean ± SD)	Active (Mean ± SD)	P Value
Active	82.7±9.55	99.55±9.99	P<0.0001

By paired t-Test, Mean heart rate after submaximal exercise in supine recovery position after 5 mins were 82.7/min which is statistically significant as compared 99.55/min in active recovery position in active individuals. P value is <0.0001.

Table 7: Comparison of heart rate recovery in sitting vs active posture in active individuals after submaximal exercise

	Sitting (Mean ± SD)	Active (Mean ± SD)	P Value
Active	91.15±15.11	99.55±9.99	p=0.0021

By paired t-Test, Mean heart rate after submaximal exercise in sitting recovery position after 5 mins were 91.15/min which is statistically significant as compared 99.55/min in active recovery position in active individuals. P value is 0.0021.

Results of intergroup comparison:

Table 8: Comparison of heart rate recovery in sedentary vs active individuals in sitting posture after submaximal exercise

	Sedentary (Mean ± SD)	Active (Mean ± SD)	P Value
Sitting	98.9±7.57	91.15±15.11	p=0.0473

By unpaired t-Test, Mean heart rate after submaximal exercise in sitting recovery position after 5 mins in sedentary individuals was 98.9/min which is statistically significant as compared 91.15/min in active individuals. P value is 0.0473.

Table 9: Comparison of heart rate recovery in sedentary vs active individuals in supine posture after submaximal exercise

	Sedentary (Mean ± SD)	Active (Mean ± SD)	P Value
Supine	90.05±5.03	82.7±9.55	p=0.0042

By unpaired t-Test, Mean heart rate after submaximal exercise in supine recovery position after 5 mins in sedentary individuals was 90.05/min which is statistically significant as compared 82.7/min inactive individuals. P value is 0.0042.

Table 10: Comparison of heart rate recovery in sedentary vs active individuals inactive posture after submaximal exercise

	Sedentary (Mean ± SD)	Active (Mean ± SD)	P Value
ACTIVE	104.65±6.05	99.2±10.14	p=0.0460

By unpaired t-Test, Mean heart rate after submaximal exercise in active recovery position after 5 mins in sedentary individuals was 104.65/min which is statistically significant as compared 99.2/min inactive individuals. P value is 0.0460.

Results of over comparison of recovery of heart rate after submaximal exercise:

Graph 1: Comparing Heart rate recovery in three recovery postures in sedentary vsactive

Graph 2: Comparing Heart rate recovery in three recovery postures in sedentary individuals with time (1,3,5,7, and 9 mins)

Graph 3: Comparing Heart rate recovery in three recovery postures inactive individuals with time (1,3,5,7, and 9 mins)

Discussion

Physical inactivity and low cardio-respiratory fitness are recognized as important causes of morbidity and mortality [3,10]. It is generally accepted that people with higher levels of physical activity tend to have higher levels of fitness and that physical activity can improve cardiorespiratory fitness [11]

The effects of the upright sitting position with active recovery on heart rate recovery has not yet been examined. Previous research has suggested faster heart rate after exercise in well-trained athletes or physically active and fit individuals [6,7]. So here we are trying to relate heart rate recovery in sitting active recovery, supine position and sitting positions of recovery and find out which recovery posture is best for the heart rate recovery after submaximal exercise and comparing it in physically active and sedentary males. Effect of posture on heart rate recovery has not been clearly studied so far in Indian setup.

The aim of the present study was to compare the heart rate recovery in three positions (supine position, upright seated position, active recovery in an upright seated position) after submaximal exercise. Additionally, we investigated the Heart rate recovery in physically active individuals vs. physically sedentary individuals in relation to different recovery positions.

In this study 40 healthy adult male individuals in the age group of 18-35 yrs. were included and were divided into two groups based on their status of being physically active or sedentary individuals [8]. Their physical fitness was assessed by a

PAR-Q questionnaire. Then their resting heart rates were recorded and then participants were asked to do submaximal cycle exercise test [8] i.e. limited period of symptomless exercise up to HR of ~86% of age-predicted maximum HR which is defined as 220 minus age of participant (Age-predicted maximal heart rate) (HRmax) [9] on cycle ergometer and then every participant will be asked to undergo a recovery protocol one after the other. During each recovery protocol, their heart rates were recorded after 1, 3, 5, 7 and 9 mins.

The results of the present study showed that active recovery in the upright seated position was the slowest recovery as compared to the other inactive positions of recovery when compared among the sedentary individuals and among the physically active individuals. The similar findings were shown by Otto F. Barak et al (8) who also concluded that regardless of the physical activity heart rate recovery after submaximal exercise was slowest in active recovery in upright seated position regardless of physical activity. Cardiovascular regulation during rest and recovery after submaximal exercise is a complex control mechanism which includes central command, baroreflex control and metaboreflex control [12].

Different recovery positions during recovery after metabolically demanding exercise may influence the interaction among these control mechanisms and results in different cardiac regulation leading to different heart recovery pattern in different recovery positions after submaximal exercise [13]. Heart rate increases during exercise this is due to the increase in the sympathetic activity and also there is a decrease in the parasympathetic activity

to the heart. When the exercise is stopped, inactive recovery (supine or upright sitting) occurs due to the cessation of primary exercise stimulus from the brain the central command and also abrupt changes in the stimuli to the baroreceptors and metaboreceptors [14]. The fall in the heart rate after cessation of exercise is the result of the sudden rise of parasympathetic activity due to the loss of central command [13]. Lying supine during recovery after exercise may be an effective means restoring Heart rate to resting level faster as gravity also helps in the faster return of the blood to the heart and thus increased venous return and thus increased stroke volume and increased cardiac output [5]. Thus, this may be the reason for faster recovery in the supine position after submaximal exercise.

When inactive recovery occurs in the upright sitting position, arterial pressure decreases rapidly [15]. Due to gravitational forces, blood from the central venous system is shifted to the lower extremities leading to decrease in the ventricular filling and decrease in the stroke volume and cardiac output [14]. The initial adjustments to orthostatic stress are mediated exclusively by the neural pathways of the autonomic nervous system [16]. To preserve blood pressure and prevent syncope, an increase in sympathetic-mediated vasomotor activity is increased and at the same time preventing sudden Heart rate fall [5,17].

During active recovery, the muscle pump facilitates the return of blood back to the heart preventing pooling in the lower extremities and thus there is an increase in sympathetic mediated vasoconstrictive activity, allowing a drop-in post-exercise heart rate. On the other hand, a central command from higher brain centers and inputs from mechanoreceptors and chemoreceptors in contracting muscles contribute to maintaining sympathetic activity to the heart (though to a lesser extent than during exercise) preventing faster fall in the heart rate [15]. As during moderate exercise when the heart rate is increased due to parasympathetic withdrawal [14], with active recovery heart rate is maintained above the resting value because continued activity will lead to the inhibition of parasympathetic system by the central command [18].

Even though heart rate recovery is slower with active recovery, lactate which got deposited in the active muscle due to high-intensity exercise, elimination of lactate might be more important for athletes than the recovery of heart rate. Present knowledge also supports the notion of the superiority of active recovery over passive recovery for lactate removal from the circulation [19,20]. During active recovery, there is an increase in the blood flow to the working muscle and it is believed to enhance the removal of lactic acid from the exercising muscle cells [21,22]. thus, leading to the

better recovery. The reduction in blood lactate concentration is associated with enhanced lactate clearance by increasing metabolic rate and systemic blood flow, thereby accelerating lactate metabolism via oxidation and gluconeogenesis [23]. Accelerating blood lactate clearance immediately post-exercise is of huge benefit for successive bouts of high-intensity exercise, particularly during athletic competitions that require multiple performances in a single day [23].

Our present study found that lying down or supine position of recovery is the fastest, irrespective of the physical activity status. Similar results were shown by Takahashi et al. [18], Buchheit et al. [5] and Otto F. Barak et al. [8] As the individual changes his body position from upright seated to supine his cardiac sympathetic nerve activity decreases and vagus nerve activity increases, as there is an increase in the venous return [14]. The increased venous return result in increased central blood volume which via arterial baroreceptors imposes a greater vagal activation and reduces heart rate and cardiac output [14]. If a similar change in activity of the two components of the autonomic nervous system occurs during the post-exercise period, a faster decrease in Heart rate would be induced in the supine position via predominance of vagus nerve activity, compared with the upright position [24].

We found that physically active individuals have faster recovery compared to the sedentary individuals. Previous studies had similar results were shown by Aubert et al., (2003) and Otto F. Barak [8] Individuals with regular physical activity showed more effective autonomic activity than the sedentary ones thus demonstrate accelerated Heart rate recovery after submaximal exercise [25-28]. Faster heart rate recovery in the supine position in physically active individuals to understand this baroreflex function adaptation should be considered [28]. As studies have shown that physically active individuals have higher baroreflex sensitivity and heart rate variability as compared to the sedentary individuals [29]. Studies also prove that with regular training and exercise heart rate variability and baroreflex sensitivity increases [26,28]. Larger blood volume and stroke volume in athletes also maintain higher activation of arterial baroreceptors leading to increased parasympathetic activation [30].

Training induces a lower level of muscle chemoreflex stimulation as a result of the increased oxidative capacity of the exercising muscle [28]. Reduced sympathetic influence on the heart activity in physically active individuals thus leads to the diminished afferent signals from muscle metaboreceptors [30] thus resulting lower resting heart rate in physically trained individuals as compared to the sedentary individuals. So, after

overall comparison of results in two groups of sedentary and physically active individuals, we can say that after submaximal exercise active recovery in an upright seated position is the slowest and recovery in the supine position is the slowest.

The results gained from the study might be of interest to clinicians wishing to prescribe exercise to clinical populations or fitness experts in dealing with the sedentary population in their everyday work; they might find a supine position to be optimal mode of recovery for patients with slower heart rate recovery or pre-syncope. Even though heart rate recovery is slower in active recovery but from the metabolic point of view (i.e. lactate elimination) it might be the optimal mode of recovery for physically active individuals.

Conclusion

Supine recovery position is the fastest heart rate recovery position and upright seated recovery position is the slowest heart rate recovery position among sedentary and among physically active individuals after submaximal exercise. When heart rate recovery was compared between sedentary and physically active individuals it was found that physically active individuals recovered heart rate faster than the sedentary individuals in all three heart rate recovery positions.

Individuals with regular physical activity showed more effective autonomic activity than the sedentary ones. We conclude that there is a definite relation between the position in which individual recovers his heart rate after exercise as results show the fastest recovery in the supine position and slowest recovery in an active upright seated position. Also, regular physical activity and heart rate recovery after exercise are also related as physically active individuals showed faster heart rate recovery in every recovery position after a session of intensive physical activity. Thus, concluding that better cardiovascular fitness will have faster heart rate recovery after exercise.

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